

HYDROGENATED CARBON FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

VGCF are short fibres produced in a single stage and since their price could well be around \$10/kg and their tensile strength approximately 2 700 MPa, their technology is of great interest.

With a length of less than 2 mm, VGCF can be produced using a VS process where the principal factor is carbon diffusion in the metallic seed previously transformed into carbon.

To produce fibres of greater length at temperatures somewhat above 1 000°C, the VLS system may be used based on the carbon compounds formed with the hydrogen having so low melting point that give rise to molten drops in this temperature range.

A review is made of the influence of the thickness of the VGCF on their tensile strength, in order to produce them with optimum mechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

The substitution of conventional materials by new materials for high market volume applications, is a option that depends principally, on first, the relative saving in weight that their use offers, and secondly, the penalty in cost/kilo that their use imposes.

In a comparative study in the automotive industry carried out by Beetz et al.¹, where steel was substituted by GFRP type composite materials, by aluminium alloys and by CFRP, it was found that while GFRP offered a 27% MS (mass saving) with a CP (cost penalty) of \$0.68/kg, and the aluminium alloy gave a 35% MS with a CP of \$2.87/kg., the CFRP offered an MS of 45% but with a CP of \$2.87/kg. The CP/MS ratio is 2.5 times worse in CFRP than in GFRP. This means that the use of CF (carbon fibre) in the automotive industry is still very limited and only 6% of CF produced in the world are intended for the land transport industry.

The CP/MP ratio of CFRP can only be improved by decreasing the price of the CF, which is impossible with the manufacturing technology of current ex-PAN fibres. The most promising possibility that has appeared on the horizon for the most economical types of CF are VGCF (Vapour Grown Carbon Fibres) to which Beck² assigned a cost of \$10/kg. This new type of CF is defined by Daumit³ as: "A non-continuous CF. For its production, a hydrocarbon vapour is combined with a catalyst source (e.g. iron particles) and hydrogen. In an elevated temperature environment, the hydrocarbon gas decomposes yielding carbon which dissolves in catalytic particles and initiates the growth of primary fibres. Such primary fibres are subsequently thickened through additional carbon deposition to a diameter of several microns and then heat-treated to enhance crystal structure and properties".

In the present paper we will deal with the formation process of VGCF and its relationship with the internal structure of VGCF. An evaluation of their mechanical properties is also performed.

2. MODELS OF FORMATION AND INTERNAL STRUCTURE

The processes for forming VGCF fibres have been widely studied⁴ and are based on a catalytic process to absorb atomic carbon that is freed into the atmosphere as a consequence of the reduction of hydrocarbon in the form of vapour. The absorbed carbon saturates the seed that is always formed by a minute metal chip: Fe, Ni, Co, etc., which are very prone to form metallic carbides. The excess carbon is expelled in the form of carbon filament as shown in Fig. 1.a.

Simultaneously with this catalytic process, the thickening process of the carbon filament takes place through slow, non-catalytic deposition of pyrolytic carbon (the atmospheres used to grow fibres are rich in H₂, as required to produce a quantity of black cake or lampblack that buries the nascent VGCF filaments and impedes their growth). When this coating is sufficiently thick, the active point has its feed interrupted and the lengthening of the fibre ceases. It is said that the growth has been poisoned.

All these models always show a mechanism based only on vapour and a solid phase. However Fig. 1.b shows three VGCF fibres produced in the normal way⁵ at a temperature of 1 060°C. The three pictures show a weld that indicates that the tip of each fibre was a drop of molten graphite. This is difficult to explain taking into account that the melting point of graphite is about 3 727 °C. During the production of SiC whiskers⁶ these VLS processes are habitually recognised.

The fibres in Fig. 1.b were produced following the operating sequence of Fig. 1.c. On a layer of pyrolytic graphite (when a substrate of graphite is no in use) the seeds were deposited using an alcoholic solution spraying of (NO₃)₃Fe. Following a first stage of reduction in H₂ at 800°C, under an atmosphere of 30% CH₄ plus 70% H₂ at 1 060°C, the growth of a fibre occurs that carries on its tip a drop of molten H₂.

We sent a sample of these fibres to Dr. Philip Honeybone of the Physics Laboratory of the University of Kent at Canterbury (UK), and he determined by analysis that the fibres contained 2% H₂ by weight. It is presumable that this hydrogen content must hold the key to the drop of molten graphite.

Fig. 2.a shows the Debye diffractogram of a sample of the conductive paint that we normally use in our SEM to bias every sample under electronmicroscope examination. This paint is simply a suspension of very fine lampblack. In Fig. 2.a we can see two x-ray diffractograms. On the one hand we see the diffraction lines of the hexagonal graphite according to the diffraction file [ASTM 23-0064]. On the other hand we see the diffraction pattern of the Pendletonite or Karpatite

(diffraction file [ASTM 28-2008]), a natural mineral having a structure similar to the chemical named coronene (C₂₄H₁₂) that contains 4% H₂ approximately. The melting point of coronene is about 434-436°C. This is a simple explanation of why when black cake is produced in a reactor by hydrocarbon reduction, the product has the aspect of a cake and not a loose powder; the coronene works as a binder.

In Fig. 2.b we see the Debye diffractogram of a VGCF some 5 - 6 μm thick germinated from a small seed. Here only the ring (002) of the hexagonal structure appears but with a marked texture (in Fig. 2.6 such ring does not show any texture at all). The enhancer or generator of the textured state of (002) hexagonal appears to be the (104) ring of the coronene phase, since because the karpatite or pendletonite is formed by directional solidification its plane (104) is formed very texturized, acting by epitaxial crystallization on the plane (002) of the hexagonal graphite, because of the similarity between the interplanary spaces of both phases.

When the VGCF under diffraction test has been produced starting with a very large seed (thick fibre), the monoclinic coronene phase (see Fig. 2.c) shows the rings (102) and (10 $\bar{2}$) with texture as well as (104) since all three have the same range of interplanary spacing. It also shows rings (101), (015) and (110) but without texturing since they have greater spacings. The hexagonal structure of the external layer, for its part, shows the ring (002) with strong texture and the (004) with weak crystalline perfection and texture, just as in ex-PAN fibres.

3. TENSILE STRENGTH OF VGCF

Fig. 3 shows the experimental values and the physical model of the tensile strength of VGCF. In order to describe this, it is easiest to accept the existence, in practice, of three basic types of VGCF, according to the internal grain that the SEM observation of their tensile fracture suggests:

- i) Thin fibres, or fibres that produce the type of diffraction pattern as shown in Fig. 2.b. Since for $\phi = 1 - 2 \mu\text{m}$ its external morphology is similar to a worm (due to the unstable growth that its small diameter imposes), its strength grows with its diameter as the increasing thickness dilutes the inter-bead neckings.
- ii) Medium thickness fibres. When structural regularity is achieved because a perfectly cylindrical fibre has been formed, and no important pyrolytic contribution has yet been received, the σ remains practically invariable at σ_1 , the value for the coronene phase.
- iii) Thick fibres. As the external pyrolytic layer becomes thicker, the average catalytic graphite/pyrolytic graphite mixture tends toward the value of σ_2 , representative of pyrolytic graphite alone. According to the model in Fig. 3.b, the tensile stress of these fibres is determined by:

$$\sigma = \sigma_1 \frac{\pi r^2}{\pi R^2} + \sigma_2 \cdot \frac{\pi (R^2 - r^2)}{\pi R^2} = \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2 (\sigma_1 - \sigma_2) + \sigma_2 \quad (1)$$

that accords with the type of experimental measurements published by ^{8 to 10}.

The same idea of dividing VGCF fibres into three categories based on their structure, is useful when using the experimental values of Fig. 3.a to formulate mathematical expressions that, according to (1), should be a polynomial of second order, so that we may establish a numerical relation between the tensile strength and the thickness of the fibres. Adjusting the experimental values (σ , ϕ) using regression functions, and choosing those functions that give the regression coefficient nearest to 1, we obtain (σ in MPa and ϕ in μm)

i) Thin fibres ($\phi < 5 \mu\text{m}$):

$$\sigma = 2\,426 + 85\phi - 8.24\phi^2 \quad (2)$$

ii) Medium thickness fibres ($5 \mu\text{m} < \phi < 12 \mu\text{m}$):

$$\sigma = 2\,526 + 46\phi - 4.7\phi^2 \quad (3)$$

iii) Thick fibres ($\phi > 12 \mu\text{m}$):

$$\sigma = 4\,200 - 126\phi - 0.4\phi^2 \quad (4)$$

According to (2) the maximum value for tensile strength is $\sigma = 2\,708$ MPa, and the ideal diameter $\phi = 5.4 \mu\text{m}$, while if we use (3) the values are $\sigma = 2\,638$ MPa and $\phi = 4.89 \mu\text{m}$.

This means that when considering VGCF production on an industrial scale, the systematic control of the σ of the product using tensile tests (ASTM Standard D 3379), may be substituted by a careful measurement of its thickness (which can be done by optical microscope) or, even better, with the additional measurement of R and r as in Fig. 3.a.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- I. The VLS process offers the possibility of producing VGCF fibres with an acceptable level of quality and uniformity.
- II. These VGCF fibres are composed in their internal zone by coronene type phases, and in their external layers by pyrolytic graphite.
- III. The tensile strength of these fibres depends on their thickness. With an optimum thickness of some $5 \mu\text{m}$ fibres of some $2\,700$ MPa can be obtained.
- IV. The σ /cost ratio for VGCF makes them the most promising candidate for the industrial manufacture of composite parts with high market volume and with good performance.

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CARBIDE LAYER

A) ALSTRUP'S MODEL.

B) THREE WELDED FIBRES.

C) VLS MODEL.

Fig 1.- Physical models for VLS growing mechanisms.

Natural graphite hexagonal, solid lines.

Monoclinic graphite: (012); ○○○○○(104); * * * *(015) ○○○○

Karpatite lines (102) and (102),

Karpatite line (104) (texturized),

A) POLYCRYSTALLINE GRAPHITE.

B) THIN VGCF.

C) THICK VGCF.

Fig 2.- Debye diffractograms of polycrystalline graphite and VGCF.

A) EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENTS .

B) PHYSICAL MODEL .

FIG 3.- RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE RUPTURE MODEL AND THE STRENGTH OF VGCF.